

**ANALYSIS OF DOCUMENTS RELATED TO THE TRAINING OF
PERSONNEL IN THE MEDICAL FIELD**
*(BASED ON THE DOCUMENTS OF THE NATIONAL ARCHIVES OF
UZBEKISTAN)*

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Abstract

This article analyzes issues related to the training of medical personnel during the early years of the establishment of the Turkestan ASSR based on archival documents. The study highlights the shortage of specialists in the healthcare system, the establishment of medical schools and short-term courses, and the processes of training medical personnel for the local population. In addition, the necessity of establishing a midwifery school and sanitary inspector courses in Samarkand is revealed through historical documents.

Keywords

Turkestan ASSR, healthcare, medical personnel, medical school, sanitary inspector, midwifery school, nursing courses, archival documents, medical education, healthcare commissariat.

Main Part

During the early years of the establishment of the Turkestan Republic, the shortage of personnel in the medical system, as in all other sectors, was one of the most pressing problems. In particular, there were almost no specialists who could speak the local language in the healthcare sector. One of the important tasks in establishing the healthcare system in the region and providing it with personnel was the organization of educational institutions. Significant information about these issues has been preserved in the documents of the Healthcare Commissariat of the

Turkestan ASSR. In particular, numerous materials concerning the training of medical personnel are reflected in the reports of healthcare commissars. It should be emphasized that after the events of the October Revolution, archival documents indicate that when recruiting personnel to Soviet state institutions, the political activities of employees during the imperial period were carefully examined before employment.

According to the documents, candidates wishing to work in the healthcare system of the Turkestan ASSR were required to complete special personal questionnaire forms. These questionnaires demanded detailed information from applicants, including their full name, gender, age, nationality, party membership, documents confirming their qualifications, property status, activities before and after October 1, 1917 (profession and official position), and the date of appointment to their position.

In 1919, the Healthcare Commissariat paid special attention to the training of personnel in the medical and sanitary fields. The fund of the Central Executive Committee of the Turkestan Republic also contains a report by I. Orlov. According to this report, training activities for healthcare and sanitary workers began in the first half of 1919. Specifically, in 1919, the Higher Medical School was established in Tashkent on the basis of the Poltoratskiy Hospital. In the first academic year, 150 students were admitted, and practical training was organized within the hospital itself.

The document states that qualified physicians such as A. Grekov, P. Borovskiy, M. Slonim, N. Tikhonovskiy, and L. Oshanin contributed to the establishment of the school. In order to address the shortage of medical and sanitary personnel in the region, the Turkestan Healthcare Commissariat organized short-term courses. These courses, established in Tashkent, enabled doctors to improve their qualifications and professional experience. Graduates of these courses were allowed to work as physicians throughout all regions of the country. In addition, four-month courses for training nursing caregivers were organized in Tashkent. In August

1919, the first graduates of these courses were employed in various medical institutions across the republic.

It should be noted that the Turkestan region covered a vast territory with a population of nearly eight million people. Under such conditions, it was impossible to solve the shortage of medical personnel solely by attracting specialists from outside the region. Therefore, the republican leadership considered it necessary to establish an educational system for training medical specialists within the country itself. However, the first graduates of the faculty completed their studies only in 1921, and the issue of fully supplying the republic with medical specialists remained unresolved. This was because the faculty was designed only to train highly educated physicians, whereas hospitals also required specialists such as physician assistants, nurses, and sanitary workers.

The timely initiatives and concerns expressed by regional healthcare administration leaders regarding the shortage of medical personnel also contributed to the establishment of various medical schools. One such school was established in the Samarkand region, and information and correspondence related to this process have also been preserved in archival documents.

A document preserved in the archives entitled “Turkestanskomu komissaru Zdravooxraneniya” states that in 1920 the head of the Samarkand Healthcare Administration, A. Abdullajonov, emphasized the urgent need to establish a midwifery school in the province. The document particularly notes that due to the shortage of such specialists in areas inhabited by the local population, the duties were being carried out by nursing caregivers.

According to the documents in the archival collections, sanitary inspector courses were organized for populated areas in the region, and students completed two months of study. The curriculum included lessons in hygiene and the care of sick and wounded individuals. Classes were conducted daily for at least two hours, totaling 335 hours during the course. Out of these 335 hours, 200 hours were devoted

to practical training such as wound dressing, caring for the sick and wounded, disinfection, and pest control.

Students of the courses also received scholarships, and after completing their studies, they were assigned to populated areas as sanitary inspectors. Based on the information in the documents, it can be concluded that the main purpose of organizing sanitary inspector training courses was not only to address healthcare problems but also to improve the severe sanitary and hygienic conditions caused by political conflicts and armed resistance movements in the region. The source materials show that sanitary inspectors were trained to provide rapid assistance to wounded military personnel.

In conclusion, during the early years of the Turkestan ASSR, the training of medical personnel was considered one of the important state tasks. The establishment of higher medical schools, short-term courses, and special educational programs served to provide the healthcare system with specialists. At the same time, the preparation of medical personnel from the local population and the development of medical education in the provinces became one of the urgent needs of that period. The issue of the shortage of local personnel in the medical field remained unresolved even by 1924.

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